

The European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics

A review of the first two WS from a data needs perspective

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REVIEW WORKSHOPS 1 & 2

- Workshop #1/3: Regulatory insights and knowledge gaps (February 7)
- Workshop #2/3: Human health risk assessment frameworks for micro- and nanoplastics (March 14)

Workshop #1/3 (February 7): Regulatory insights and knowledge gaps

- Activities for adaption of policy to risk potential of MNP revealed some deficits (see Bertato and Kobe)
- MNP sources (incl. sectoral impacts) and fate (breakdown mechanisms and pathways)
- Human health: scientific evidence on human health effects still limited
- Environment: What are the key risks? Effects on ecosystem functions? Impacts „beyond smoking guns“? (T. Dan Nielsen, EEA)
- All MNP shall be covered: Differences between types and sizes? Analytical methods for small particles?
- For exposure assessment (in particular human exposure): more precise estimates needed, limited data for some foods and drinking water

Workshop #2/3 (March 14): Human health risk assessment frameworks for micro- and nanoplastics

- ECHA identified MP as of „extreme persistence“ besides the tendency to accumulate in the environment → exceeding effect thresholds; currently not possible to determine thresholds for MP
→ should be treated like PBT/vPvB substances
(Oliver Peters, BAuA)

increase non-knowledge
(known and unknown
unknowns)

-increasing non-knowledge
complicates risk
assessment, reduce
value of results in
risk assessment

Workshop #2/3: Human health risk assessment frameworks for micro- and nanoplastics

- First approaches of risk assessment frameworks for MNP based on experience with nanoparticles
(PlasticHeal, S.F. Hansen / Polyrisk, A. Haase / AURORA, M. Boyles / EPA, A.M. Jarabek)
- Risk assessment frameworks for nanoparticles not fully transferable to MNPs
- Non-knowledge can be reduced by grouping and data can be obtained in a structured way by integrated approaches of testing and assessment (IATAs)
(see approach of POLYRISK, A. Haase)

RISK ASSESSMENT

- Still many data need to be determined
- E.g. prediction of exposure:
 - mass flow analysis → applications, masses & release factors over the whole life cycle, release of/degradation to MNP, transfer between technical and natural compartments etc.

RESPONSIBLE HANDLING OF NON-KNOWLEDGE

- We will never fully know the impact of a technology (a material)
→ Risk assessment should be adapted to the availability and quality of the data
- Precautionary principle → preventive policy actions!
(see Bertato and Kobe, 1st WS)
- Non-knowledge is also generated by properties of the technology itself
(e.g. persistence of a material in the natural environment)
→ suitable design of a material can reduce non-knowledge!

AIM OF CUSP WORKSHOP III ON DATA NEEDS

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- Address issues related to collection of input information required for characterisation of MNP risk by
 1. Collecting, structuring data/format/quality requirements
 2. Discuss options to solve the problems
 3. Quality assessment for studies that produce the data
 4. Review data sources incl. the character of the included data

Thank you!

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